

Author's Accepted Manuscript. Full article published in: Tropical Conservation Science
Volume 10: 1–8, and available at: DOI: 10.1177/1940082917735416

**The fate of an Amazonian savanna: government land-use planning endangers
sustainable development in Amapá, the most protected Brazilian state**

Short Running title: The fate of an Amazonian savanna

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Abstract

While Amapá is the most protected Brazilian state, the same level of protection does not extend to its savannas which are currently suffering increased pressure from threats including large-scale agriculture, particularly the expansion of soybean plantations. In September 2016, the Government of Amapá presented a zoning proposal (ZSC) that reserves most of the savannas for agricultural activities. Here we outline how the methodology employed is flawed because it does not include fauna surveys, ecosystem services evaluations or an assessment of the social importance of the savannas. The ZSC authors admit that, contrary to Brazilian legislation, the zoning was carried out with the single intention of increasing agriculture production. Current knowledge indicates that Amapá's savannas are rich in biodiversity, including endemic and threatened species, and are also home to a rich culture of traditional populations. These savannas are important providers of ecosystem services that, if intact, could represent around US\$ 1.52 billion annually. We hold that the ZSC should be reformulated, with fair participation of stakeholders, in accordance with Brazil's legal requirements. At least 30% of the savannas should be protected, local family farming should be supported, and the rights of traditional peoples must now be assured through recognition of their land rights.

Keywords: Agriculture; Amazon; Biodiversity conservation; Cerrado; Ecosystem services; Land-use policy; Soybean plantation.

Introduction

Brazil is a key player in global biodiversity conservation. The state of Amapá, situated in the far north-east of the Amazon region, plays an important role in Brazil's conservation network with more than 95% of its original vegetation being well-preserved and close to 70% of its extent lying within protected areas (PAs) (Drummond, Dias, & Brito, 2008; SEMA-AP, 2015). However, this protection does not extend to the 10,021 km² of savanna vegetation that stretches along the eastern side of the state (Fig. 1), forming a patchwork of savannah interspersed with moist broad-leaf forests, flooded forests, floodplains and mangroves in an "Amazonian savanna complex" (Carvalho & Mustin, 2017; SEMA-AP, 2012).

Only 917.69 km² (~9.2%) of the savannas in Amapá are legally protected, and even less (40.24 km², or 0.4%) are in "strictly protected" areas. A further ~27 km² (~0.3%) are protected by Indigenous Lands, and ~850.42 km² (~8.5%) by PAs within which various kinds of use are allowed (Mustin et al., In Press; see also: Nogueira, Yanai, Vasconcelos, Graça, & Fearnside, 2017). This lack of adequate protection is of particular concern because the savannas of Amapá are suffering increased pressure from threats such as large-scale agriculture and commercial silviculture (Carvalho & Mustin, 2017; Silva, 2016). Similar to those in the state of Roraima before them (Barbosa, Campos, Pinto, & Fearnside, 2007), the savannas of Amapá are now considered to be the "final frontier" for soybean plantations in Brazil (Silva, 2016). Low land costs

associated with expected improvement in infrastructure to allow for the export of produce are attracting soybean farmers to Amapá (Silva, 2016). The federal government transferred the ownership of large tracts of land, including savannas, to the state government (Federal Decree 8713/2016 - Brazil, 2016), which is accelerating the process of “regularisation” of land ownership by local farmers who can then sell their lands to soybean farmers at cheap prices. This situation is evolving rapidly, with the area planted with soybeans in Amapá increasing by >200% in just three years (from 45.5 km² in 2013 to 148.6 km² in 2016) (IBGE, 2017). This increase has been entirely concentrated in two municipalities plus the state capital: Itaubal, Tartarugalzinho and Macapá (Fig. 2a). Tartarugalzinho and Macapá each also contain more than 1700 km² of savanna (Fig. 2b), and their savannas are some of the least protected in the state (Fig. 2c). Projections suggest the area planted with soybeans in the savannas of Amapá could increase to 4,000 km² by 2026 (Silva, 2016), which would represent ~40% of the total area of savanna habitat in the state. In addition, of the 138 “*quilombos*” (traditional communities of descendants of escaped African slaves) that reside in the savannas of Amapá, 27 are located within these three municipalities (Fig. 1), highlighting the socio-cultural importance of these areas. Therefore, before considering the expansion of large-scale agriculture in the region that is planned by the state government in its recent “socio-environmental zoning” of the savannas in Amapá (*Zoneamento Socioambiental*

do Cerrado, or “ZSC” in Portuguese) (GEA, SETEC, IEPA, NOT, & EMBRAPA, 2016), we hold that social and environmental factors must be considered.

On September 21th, 2016, the ZSC was presented to the members of four state committees (Water Resources, the Environment, Sustainable Rural Development, and the Amapá Fund for Rural Development). The aim of this zoning document is to facilitate land-use planning for the areas of savanna in the state of Amapá. The ZSC quantifies current use of Amapá’s savannas and recommends the expansion of agricultural activities (Fig. 3). However, the zoning document is flawed. Here we highlight its key shortcomings and suggest ways in which the proposed land-use plan could be improved to better balance the three pillars of sustainable development: social, environmental and economic (United Nations, 2016).

Brazilian zoning legislation versus the ZSC

The new Brazilian Forest Code (Brazil, 2012) specifies a deadline of 2017 for all Brazilian states to submit an Ecological-Economic Zoning (*Zoneamento Ecológico Econômico*, or “ZEE”), which should be prepared following the specific guidelines laid out by the Federal Ministry of the Environment (Brazil, 2006). The ZSC document uses nomenclature different from that which is legally recognised (i.e., ZSC vs. ZEE) and openly admits to not having followed the legal guidelines that would allow for its consideration as a ZEE (GEA et al., 2016). For example, according to the guidelines a

ZEE should be carried out for the entire state, in contrast with Amapá's ZSC that considers only areas of savanna vegetation. Further, the ZSC was presented to the four state committees without having been previously presented to civil society in the state. This goes against Decree 4.297/2002 (Brazil, 2002a), which states that, for a ZEE to be approved at the federal level, it must have resulted from an open and participatory process involving key stakeholders. The government decision to issue a zoning document that does not meet the requirements set out in Brazilian federal law (Brazil, 2002a) appears to represent a step in the direction of a business-as-usual scenario rather than a prioritisation of sustainable development and biodiversity conservation.

The methodology used to develop the ZSC is not adequate as a basis for a socio-environmental zoning of the savannas. The ZSC is based on soil classification and mapping derived from just 16 soil pits and an unspecified number of inventories of woody vegetation. Contrary to Brazilian legislation (Brazil, 2002a), no assessments were made in the field regarding fauna, ecosystem services or the social importance of the savannas, and no plans were included for monitoring and minimising social and environmental impacts. Indeed, the ZSC authors themselves admit that the zoning was carried out with the single intention of increasing the production of “*grãos*” (grains and pulses), especially soybeans, as a way to promote the economic development of the state. Despite obvious inadequacies in the methodologies used, the ZSC presents a plan to zone the savannas in Amapá. The conclusions made in the report regarding

appropriate land uses across the savanna habitats cannot be supported by the methodology employed, and, as such, the ZSC should be disregarded. In the following sections, we highlight some specific requirements that should have been considered in the ZSC and that are essential for an appropriate zoning.

Biodiversity inventories

No information was included in the ZSC regarding the faunal diversity of Amapá's savanna habitats. Despite just a small number of inventories having been carried out, evidence already shows a rich faunal community that varies across the savannas. Three-hundred-and-fifty species of invertebrates, 200 species of birds, 108 mammals (including 38 bat species), 26 species of fish and 41 species of amphibian and 26 reptile species have already been recorded from Amapá's Amazonian savannas (Mustin et al., In Press). The known fauna includes six mammals considered to be threatened, following the classification of the World Conservation Union (IUCN): *Myrmecophaga tridactyla* Linnaeus, 1758, *Priodontes maximus* (Kerr, 1792), *Tapirus terrestris* Linnaeus, 1758, *Tayassu pecari* (Link, 1795), *Alouatta belzebul* (Linnaeus, 1766) and *Pteronura brasiliensis* (Gmelin, 1788) (IUCN, 2016). In addition, Amapá's savanna habitats are considered to be an "important bird area" due to their relevance for the conservation of two bird species – the shrike-like tanager *Neothraupis fasciata* and the

rufous-sided pygmy tyrant *Euscarthmus rufomarginatus* (De Luca, Develey, Bencke, & Goerck, 2009).

Floristic diversity was only partially evaluated, considering only three woody species (GEA et al., 2016). As such, the ZSC ignores the fact that 378 species of plants have been recorded in the savannas of the state, of which ~60% are non-woody (Costa-Neto, Miranda, & Rocha, 2017). Amapá's Amazonian savannas are also home to two endemic plant species - *Axonopus amapaensis* G.A.Black and *Borreria amapaensis* E.L.Cabral & Bacigalupo (Costa-Neto et al., 2017; Rocha, Miranda, & Costa-Neto, 2014) – whose distribution was also not included in the ZSC.

Stakeholder participation

Amapá's savannas are also home to a rich culture of traditional and indigenous populations that have strong links with the land upon which they live. In particular, 138 *quilombos* are located in these savannas (Silva, 2012), of which 31 have their lands officially recognised by the Brazilian Federal Government (Colares, 2010). Brazilian law states that these lands, once recognised, cannot be sold, mortgaged, rented, donated or acquired by adverse possession, and that the deed to the land must be collective and in the name of an association of inhabitants (Prioste, Alves, & Camerini, 2011). This means that recognised *quilombos* represent land that is unavailable for the market as it stands in the current agri-business model (Prioste et al., 2011). As such, this discrepancy

between the number of *quilombos* in Amapá's savannas and the officially recognised number could be, in part, due to conflict with powerful agricultural producers and businesses who own large tracts of land and who seek to block the recognition of these *quilombos* in order to maintain these lands available for purchase (Prioste et al., 2011). Indeed, 44.4% of the agricultural land in Brazil is owned by just 1% of the landowners (OXFAM, 2016). Large landholders therefore have a strong influence in Brazilian politics and, by extension, on the granting of land rights to the *quilombolas* (people who live in *quilombos*) (Prioste et al., 2011). As such, the lack of recognition of the other 107 *quilombos*, together with the land-use changes proposed in the ZSC that identify large areas of Amapá's savannas for large-scale agriculture, leaves large areas open to procurement and development for agri-business.

Economic importance

Beyond their importance for local communities and for biodiversity conservation, the savannas in Amapá are important providers of ecosystem services, such as carbon storage, climate regulation, water and nutrient cycling, pollination, seed dispersal, natural pest control, ecotourism, and the production of fruits, fish and other natural products. Considering the average value of ecosystem services provided by the world's savannas (Costanza et al., 2014) and the area occupied by savannas in the state, we estimate that, if intact, Amapá's savannas could provide the equivalent of around US\$

1.52 billion annually in ecosystem services. However, it is important to note that a significant part of this value has already been changed, given that 30.7% of the area has already been converted to agriculture, silviculture and other productive uses (GEA et al., 2016). The loss of ecosystem services would increase further if the zoning suggested by the ZSC were to be implemented, converting a further 37.3% of the area to soy plantations and pasture (see Fig. 3). Most of Amapá's savannas are moderately vulnerable to erosion (Brazil, 1974), meaning that the land could rapidly degrade if converted to plantations and pasture, reducing the ecosystem value of these areas. In addition, the application of pesticides close to water bodies can compromise water quality, with impacts on biodiversity, fish production, ecotourism and human health (Schwarzenbach, Egli, Hofstetter, von Gunten, & Wehrli, 2010), since some of the flooded environments in the savannas are used for swimming by the local population and by weekend visitors.

Conclusions

The relevance of Amapá's savannas to biodiversity, local communities and ecosystem services indicates that these habitats need greater protection. Specifically, most of the area currently within PAs is not sufficiently protected. It is also essential that new protected areas be created to increase the area protected to at least 30%. Highly biodiverse areas in which less than 30% of the original vegetation remains can be

considered “hotspots” for conservation (Myers, Mittermeier, Mittermeier, Da Fonseca, & Kent, 2000), and 30% is also considered to be the “fragmentation threshold” (Pardini, Arruda Bueno, Gardner, Prado, & Metzger, 2010). Indeed, the Brazilian Ministry of Environment recognises Amapá’s savannas as being in the highest level of priority for conservation and indicates the need for establishment of a strictly protected area in the central portion of Amapá’s savannas (Brazil, 2002b). However, expansion of protected areas should not focus only on one area of the state (Fig. 2). Amapá’s savannas encompass different soil types and phytophysionomies (Fig. 1; Brazil, 1974; GEA et al., 2016), indicating a heterogeneous distribution of biodiversity. Protecting just one part of the savanna complex risks leaving part of its biodiversity unprotected.

Amapá’s savannas are host to a rich and heterogeneous biodiversity that remains little-known and that must be considered before any kind of large-scale land-use change takes place. A more complete inventory of the biodiversity of these savannas, covering their full extent and including longer-term sampling, would certainly increase the list of known species. Indeed, we assert that the ZSC could have been used as an opportunity to increase knowledge of biodiversity in the state’s savannas; instead, the ZSC in its current form represents a real and serious threat to savanna conservation.

The ZSC also represents a threat to the way-of-life of the *quilombola* populations. We recommend that any zoning document must be produced in partnership with representatives of these communities and should identify strategies to avoid

cultural deterioration and other negative impacts on the traditional and indigenous populations, including impacts resulting from modification of the ecosystem.

We recognise that agricultural production has the potential to generate wealth for the state of Amapá, but we emphasize that the savannas in their preserved state also provide economic benefits to the state via their ecosystem services. We are not against agricultural production. Indeed, we all require food production. However, given that a substantial part of the food consumed in Brazil is produced by family farming, and that this employs 70% of the country's rural workers (Brazil, 2011), we see small-scale family farming as the solution required to support truly sustainable development in the state of Amapá. In contrast, the type of agribusiness suggested in the Socio-Environmental Zoning of the Cerrado (ZSC) generates very few jobs for local people and threatens traditional ways of life. In addition, since most of the production will be destined for export, soy plantations in Amapá will not contribute to reductions in the price of local food and will represent various environmental threats that may also translate into impacts on the health and well-being of local populations (e.g. Fearnside, 2001; Fearnside, & Figueiredo, 2015). Furthermore, owing largely to inefficient policies, lack of support for local family farmers (either financial or technological) and lack of investment in infrastructure, the production of rice, beans, maize, and oranges, which are among the most important family-farm products in the state, shrank continuously in Amapá over the course of the last decade (GEA et al., 2014; IBGE,

2017). This highlights a rationale for the state government to consider increasing support to family farms in order to recover their productivity and increase employment instead of choosing to facilitate commodity production in a highly unequal land-distribution system. Sustainable development, which is among the stated objectives of the ZSC, requires economic development in concert with the maintenance of environmental equilibrium and guarantees of social justice. As such, achieving sustainable development in Amapá will not be possible without a participatory and open planning process that provides for the conservation of representative areas of Amapá's savannas, generates employment for local people, and protects and endorses the rights of traditional and indigenous populations.

Acknowledgments

We are grateful to C. R. Silva for valuable considerations during our first discussions on this subject. We are also grateful to an anonymous reviewer who made valuable comments on a first version of this paper, and to Dr Jane McDonald who kindly revised the manuscript for English. R.H.H is supported by CNPq (447432/2014-1), the Conservation Leadership Programme (02327917), the Rufford Foundation (22322-1) and Primate Conservation Inc. (PCI: 1357). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie

Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 706680, which supported K.M. P.M.F. thanks CNPq (305880/2007-1; 304020/2010-9; 573810/2008-7; 575853/2008-5), Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado do Amazonas (FAPEAM: 708565), Instituto Nacional de Pesquisas da Amazônia (INPA: PRJ15.125) and the Brazilian Research Network on Climate Change (Rede Clima) (FINEP 01.13.0353-00). J.M.C.S. is supported by the University of Miami and Swift Action Fund. WDC is supported by a post-doctoral scholarship (CAPES – PNPd).

References

- Barbosa, R. I., Campos, C., Pinto, F., & Fearnside, P. M. (2007). The “lavrados” of Roraima: Biodiversity and conservation of Brazil's Amazonian savannas. *Functional Ecosystems and Communities*, 1(1), 30-42.
- Brazil. (1974). *Projeto Radam – Folha NA/NB.22-Macapá: Geologia, geomorfologia, solos, vegetação e uso potencial da terra*. Rio de Janeiro, BR: Departamento de Produção Mineral.
- Brazil. (2002a). Decreto 4297/2002. Retrieved from http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/decreto/2002/d4297.htm
- Brazil. (2002b). *Biodiversidade brasileira: Avaliação e identificação de áreas e ações prioritárias para conservação, utilização sustentável e repartição dos benefícios*

- da biodiversidade nos biomas brasileiros*. Brasília, BR: MMA (Ministério do Meio Ambiente).
- Brazil. (2006). Diretrizes Metodológicas para o Zoneamento Ecológico-Econômico do Brasil. Retrieved from <http://www.mma.gov.br/destaques/item/7529-diretrizes-metodologicas>
- Brazil. (2011). Agricultura Familiar - Segunda Parte. Retrieved from <http://sistemas.mda.gov.br/arquivos/1184712943.pdf>
- Brazil. (2012). Lei nº 12.651, de 25 de maio de 2012. Retrieved from http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_ato2011-2014/2012/lei/112651.htm
- Brazil. (2016). Decreto Nº 8.713, de 15 de abril de 2016. Regulamenta a Lei no 10.304, de 5 de novembro de 2001, no que se refere à transferência ao domínio do Estado do Amapá de terras pertencentes à União. Retrieved from http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_ato2015-2018/2016/decreto/D8713.htm
- Carvalho, W. D., & Mustin, K. (2017). The little known, highly threatened and under-protected Amazonian Savannas. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 1(4), 0100.
doi:10.1038/s41559-017-0100
- Colares, M. S. P. (2010). *Comunidades remanescentes de quilombos em Macapá: Mapeamento dos resultados da política de assistência social*. (Masters dissertation), Universidade Federal Fluminense, Niterói, BR.

- Costa-Neto, S. V., Miranda, I., & Rocha, A. E. S. (2017). Flora das savanas do estado do Amapá. In A. Bastos, J. Miranda-Júnior, & R. Silva (Eds.), *Conhecimento e manejo sustentável da biodiversidade amapaense* (pp. 65-94). São Paulo: Blucher.
- Costanza, R., de Groot, R., Sutton, P., van der Ploeg, S., Anderson, S. J., Kubiszewski, I., . . . Turner, R. K. (2014). Changes in the global value of ecosystem services. *Global Environmental Change*, 26, 152-158.
doi:<http://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2014.04.002>
- De Luca, A. C., Develey, P. F., Bencke, G. A., & Goerck, J. M. (2009). *Áreas importantes para a conservação das aves no Brasil. Parte II – Amazônia, Cerrado e Pantanal*. São Paulo-BR: SAVE Brasil.
- Drummond, J. A., Dias, T. C. A. C., & Brito, D. M. C. (2008). *Atlas das Unidades de Conservação do Amapá*. Macapá, BR: IBAMA-AP/SEMA-AP.
- Fearnside, P. M. (2001). Soybean cultivation as a threat to the environment in Brazil. *Environmental Conservation*, 28(01), 23-38. doi:10.1017/S0376892901000030
- Fearnside, P. M., & Figueiredo, A. M. (2015). China's Influence on Deforestation in Brazilian Amazonia: A Growing Force in the State of Mato Grosso. In R. Ray, K. Gallagher, A. López, & C. Sanborn (Eds.), *China and Sustainable Development in Latin America: The Social and Environmental Dimension*. (pp. 229-265). New York, USA: Anthem Press.

GEA (Governo do Estado do Amapá), SETEC (Secretaria Estadual de Ciência e Tecnologia em Macapá), IEPA (Instituto de Pesquisas Científicas e Tecnológicas do Estado do Amapá), NOT (Núcleo de Ordenamento Territorial), & EMBRAPA (Empresa Brasileira de Pesquisa Agropecuária). (2016). *Zoneamento Socioambiental do Cerrado do Estado do Amapá: Relatório técnico sintetizado*. Macapá, Brazil: IEPA.

GEA (Governo do Estado do Amapá), SETEC (Secretaria Estadual de Ciência e Tecnologia em Macapá), IEPA (Instituto de Pesquisas Científicas e Tecnológicas do Estado do Amapá), SEMA-AP (Secretaria de Estado do Meio Ambiente – Amapá), IMAP (Instituto do Meio Ambiente e de Ordenamento Territorial do Amapá), SDR-AP (Secretaria de Estado do Desenvolvimento Rural – Amapá), . . . IEF-AP (Instituto Estadual de Florestas - Amapá). (2014). Relatório Final - Zoneamento Ecológico-Econômico do Cerrado do Amapá: Estratégias para a Sustentabilidade e Desenvolvimento Inclusivo. Retrieved from <http://www.infoteca.cnptia.embrapa.br/infoteca/handle/doc/1009782>

IBGE. (Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística). (2004) Mapa de Vegetação do Brasil. Scale 1:5.000.000. Retrieved from www.ibge.gov.br

IBGE (Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística). (2017). Banco de dados SIDRA. Senso Agropecuário. Retrieved from

<http://www.sidra.ibge.gov.br/bda/tabela/listabl.asp?c=1612&z=&o=>.

<http://www.sidra.ibge.gov.br/bda/tabela/listabl.asp?c=1612&z=&o=>

IUCN (International Union for Conservation of Nature). (2016). The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. Version 2016-2. Retrieved from <http://www.iucnredlist.org>

Mustin, K., Carvalho, W.D.C, Hilário, R.R., Costa-Neto, S.V., Silva, C., Vasconcelos, I.M., Castro, I.J., Eilers, V., Kauano, E.E., Mendes-Junior, R.N.G., Funi, C., Fearnside, P.M., Silva, J.M.C., Euler, A.M.C., Toledo, J.J. (In Press).

Biodiversity, threats and conservation challenges in the Cerrado of Amapá, and Amazonian savanna. *Nature Conservation*

Myers, N., Mittermeier, R. A., Mittermeier, C. G., Da Fonseca, G. A., & Kent, J.

(2000). Biodiversity hotspots for conservation priorities. *Nature*, 403(6772), 853-858. doi:10.1038/35002501

Nogueira, E. M., Yanai, A. M., Vasconcelos, S. S., Graça, P. M. L. A., & Fearnside, P.

M. (2017). Carbon stocks and losses to deforestation in protected areas in Brazilian Amazonia. *Regional Environmental Change*, doi:10.1007/s10113-017-1198-1

OXFAM. (2016). Desterrados: Tierra, poder y desigualdad en América Latina.

Retrieved from <https://www.oxfam.org/es/informes/desterrados-tierra-poder-y-desigualdad-en-america-latina>

- Pardini, R., Arruda Bueno, A., Gardner, T. A., Prado, P. I., & Metzger, J. P. (2010). Beyond the fragmentation threshold hypothesis: regime shifts in biodiversity across fragmented landscapes. *PloS One*, 5(10), e13666. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0013666
- Prioste, F. G. V., Alves, C. C. N., & Camerini, J. C. B. (2011). Quem tem medo da Constituição Federal? Quilombolas e direito ao território. In S. Sauer & W. Almeida (Eds.), *Terras e territórios na Amazônia: demandas, desafios e perspectivas* (pp. 297-316). Brasília, BR: Editora Universidade de Brasília.
- Rocha, A. E. S., Miranda, I. S., & Costa-Neto, S. V. (2014). Composição florística e chave de identificação das Poaceae ocorrentes nas savanas costeiras amazônicas, Brasil. *Acta Amazonica*, 44, 301-314. doi:10.1590/1809-4392201305173.
- Schwarzenbach, R. P., Egli, T., Hofstetter, T. B., von Gunten, U., & Wehrli, B. (2010). Global water pollution and human health. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 35, 109-136.
- SEMA-AP (Secretaria de Estado do Meio Ambiente – Estado do Amapá). (2012). *Vegetação do Estado do Amapá*. Macapá, BR: Governo do Estado.
- SEMA-AP (Secretaria de Estado do Meio Ambiente – Estado do Amapá). (2015). *Boletim do desmatamento no estado do Amapá - Biênio 2013/2014*. Macapá, BR: Governo do Estado do Amapá.

- SEMA-AP (Secretaria de Estado do Meio Ambiente – Estado do Amapá). (2016) Shapes. Retrieved from <http://www.sema.ap.gov.br/interno.php?dm=745>
- Silva, E. (2016). A última fronteira da soja. *Revista Globo Rural: Editora Globo*, 371, 28-33.
- Silva, M. G. (2012). *Territórios quilombolas no Estado do Amapá: Um diagnóstico*. XXI Encontro Nacional de Geografia, Uberlândia-MG. Anais do XXI Encontro Nacional de Geografia Agrária, Uberlândia, BR.
- United Nations. (2016). *Global Sustainable Development Report 2016*. New York, NY, USA: United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs.
- WDPA (World Database on Protected Areas). (2016) World Database on Protected Areas. Retrieved from <https://www.protectedplanet.net/>

Figure legends

Figure 1 Distribution of the four main savanna habitat types, eucalyptus plantations and forest patches within the savanna domain, in the state of Amapá (based on the Brazilian Ministry for the Environment's vegetation cover map for the Amazon (IBGE, 2004). Grey lines show the boundaries of the 16 municipalities that make up the state. Black dots show the locations of “*quilombos*” (traditional communities of descendants of escaped African slaves) mapped using data from SEMA-AP (2016).

Figure 2 (a) Average annual increase in area planted with soybeans between 2013 and 2016 (IBGE, 2017), per municipality in the state of Amapá, (b) Total amount of savanna habitats (based on the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics vegetation cover map for the Amazon) (IBGE, 2004), and (c) the proportion of total area of savanna habitats contained within any kind of protected area (calculated using the shapefiles of “Conservation Units” and Indigenous Lands available from the Amapá State Environmental Secretariat (SEMA-AP, 2016) and the World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA, 2016).

Figure 3 Current (brown) and planned future (blue) land uses in the savannas of Amapá, according to the state government's Socio-Environmental Zoning of the Cerrado (ZSC).

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Average annual increase of soybean plantations 2013 - 2016 (km²)

- 2.43
- 7.28
- 24.65
- NA

Total amount of savanna habitats (km²)

- 0
- <100
- 100 - 500
- 500 - 1000
- 1000 - 1500
- >1500

Proportion of savanna habitats protected

- 0
- <1
- 1 - 10
- 10 - 50
- 50 - 75
- 75 - 100
- NA

Fig. 3

